

Lagrangian/Action Formalism As a Flow Scheme

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In a previous note (1), we argued that one may obtain either the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equation from the classical free particle Action = Integral dt L = T L(v) by writing $v=X/T$ and using: $p= dAction/dx$ partial and $-E = dAction/dt$ partial. This may be used together with an energy-momentum relationship $E=pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic) or $EE=pp + mm$ (relativistic) to create an eigenfunction equation by using $\exp(i Action)$ as a solution. This is equivalent to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

In (2), we argued that if one generalizes momentum p to Ev where $E(v)$ is energy and uses nonrelativistic Lagrangian equations: $p=dL/dv$ and $H=E= pv-L$, one may find the relativistic Lagrangian for a free particle which in turn yields $p= d/dx (TL)$ partial and $-E= d/dt (TL)$ partial i.e. the form of energy and momentum for a free particle in special relativity.

In this brief note, we argue that the Action/Lagrangian formalism for a free particle seems to follow directly from a flow(flux) type equation namely: $d/dx Action$ partial = $p = Ev$ (= $m_0 v$ nonrelativistic limit). If energy is flowing out of a region given by the usual Gaussian flux equation d/dx function (i.e. grad dot vector) represented by $d/dx Action$ partial, then one is losing energy $E(v)$ in this region. Thus $d/dt Action$ partial = $-E$. As a result, one should analyze the problem in special relativity i.e. use $p=E(v) v$ (but no explicit form for $E(v)$) and then take the nonrelativistic limit to get the nonrelativistic approximation.

As a result, assuming a flow problem with a function Action(x,t) leads to the Lagrangian formalism. From this one may obtain the forms of special relativity, classical equations of motion and quantum mechanics for a free particle (relativistic or nonrelativistic).

Special Relativity and the Free Particle Lagrangian/Action

In (2) we noted that one may take nonrelativistic Lagrange equations i.e.

$$dL/dv = p \quad \text{and} \quad H(\text{Hamiltonian})=E(\text{energy}) = pv - L \quad ((1)) \quad L=\text{Lagrangian}$$

and then make the identification:

$$p=Ev \quad \text{i.e.} \quad p=\text{momentum} \quad \text{is energy flow} \quad ((2)).$$

In that case one obtains the differential equation for a free particle L i.e.

$$1/v (dL/dv) = v dL/dv - L \quad ((3)) \quad \text{which yields:} \quad L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv} \quad ((3))$$

Using: $p=dL/dv$, $p= m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) and $p=Ev$ yields E .

In other words, one obtains special relativistic behaviour.

In this note, we suggest that $p=Ev$ suggests a flow scheme and that the notion of Action for a free particle and its properties under d/dx (partial) and d/dt (partial) may be related directly to flow. In other words, this would yield a recipe for obtaining the Action and thus the Lagrangian.

Action and Lagrangian for a Free Particle from Relativistic Flow Scheme

First of all, we use the form of special relativity i.e. $p=E(v)v$ (and not $p = m_0 v$) in order to establish a flow scheme. The nonrelativistic form should arise as an approximation. If one has flow (flux) described by $p=Ev$, one should be able to use the Gauss form grad dot vector to describe it. This suggests a one dimensional function Action(x,t) and:

$$dAction(x,t) / dx \text{ (partial)} = E(v) v \quad ((4)) \text{ Gauss type equation in one dimension}$$

If energy $E(v)$ is flowing out of a region, then one is losing this energy in time at x so one has a second equation:

$$dAction/ dt \text{ (partial)} = -E(v) \quad ((5))$$

From ((5)) one may postulate the form: Action= TL(v) as d/dT acting on the first term yields $L(v)$. Acting on the second term, one has: $T dL/dv \times d/dT (1/T)$. $X/T=v$ and $T/T=1$ so this form is fine. Using ((4)) one finds that: $T dL/dv (1/T) dx/x = p$ or $dL/dv = p$. This is a result from Lagrange theory i.e. L is the Lagrangian in this scenario.

Thus, it seems that using special relativity and the idea of flow (flux) with Gauss' equation and the idea that d/dt (partial) $A(x,t) = -E$ (as one loses energy E), one obtains the Action and Lagrangian together with the result $dL/dv = p$ and $pv-L = H=E$ for a free particle.

One may proceed to derive the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equation for a free particle from this formalism (1) or to try to derive the classical equations of motion $d/dt dL/dv = -dV/dx$.

Conclusion

By starting with special relativity (although no explicit form except the idea of $E(v)$), one may define a flow (flux) of $E(v)v$ where v is velocity. Using Gauss' law one has:

$$d/dx \text{ (partial)} A(x,t) = E(v) v \text{ where } A \text{ is an unknown function.}$$

If energy $E(v)$ is flowing out then at a tiny dx region, one must be losing this energy in time so:

$$d/dt \text{ (partial)} A(x,t) = -E(v).$$

If one uses $A(x,t) = TL(v)$ one finds that $p=Ev = dL/v$ and $H=E = pv-L$. One may use these two equations without knowing the results of special relativity and derive (as in (1)) $p=mv / \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) and $E = m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$). Furthermore, one may use the free particle Action

formalism to derive both nonrelativistic and relativistic quantum mechanics for a free particle (1) and the form of special relativity (2). In addition, the free particle Lagrangian may be generalized to yield Newton's equations of motion.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Klein-Gordon Equation, $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ [Propagator] and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Special Relativity From Nonrelativistic Lagrangian Formalism? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)